

The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change

A Practitioner Extension of the J-Curve Framework for Agile and Iterative Technology Transformation

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Abstract

The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change is a practitioner framework extending the author's J-Curve of Change (Viney, 2005) into the context of iterative and agile technology delivery. It proposes that agile sprint cadence does not eliminate the performance disruption described by the J-Curve — it distributes it. Rather than a single large performance dip, organisations undergoing agile transformation experience a series of smaller oscillations repeated at sprint cadence, producing cumulative cognitive load that is difficult to observe in aggregate. Without deliberate change management, this cumulative effect produces a measurable gap between the end state actually achieved and the desired state: what the author terms the 'dead loss of poor adoption'. The framework challenges the prevalent assumption that agile methods render structured change management unnecessary, drawing on Kahneman's dual-process theory and the Zeigarnik effect to explain why many small changes may impose a greater total cognitive burden on affected individuals than a single large one. The paper argues that agile does not make change management redundant — it makes it differently necessary: persistent rather than episodic, embedded rather than separate, and focused on minimising the residual cognitive load of continuous iteration rather than managing a single transformational dip.

Keywords: *change management, agile, J-Curve, Wiggly Curve, cognitive load, Zeigarnik effect, Kaizen, Kaikaku, user adoption, iterative change, organisational performance*

1. Introduction

The J-Curve of Change (Viney, 2005) describes a well-documented phenomenon in organisational transformation: when significant change is introduced, performance characteristically deteriorates before it recovers and ultimately surpasses the prior baseline. This pattern, shaped like the letter J when plotted against time, has been widely cited across change management, project management, healthcare, education, and AI transformation contexts. The framework has been adopted by practitioners worldwide and cited in peer-reviewed journals, academic encyclopaedias, and academic monographs.

Since its original publication, one of the most frequently observed adaptations of the J-Curve has been its application within the agile and Kanban development community. The emergence of iterative, sprint-based delivery methodologies over the past two decades has prompted a recurring question: does the J-Curve still apply when change is delivered incrementally rather than in a single large release? And with it, a related assumption: that agile's iterative nature reduces the disruption of change sufficiently that structured business change management is no longer required.

This paper presents the Wiggly Curve of Agile Change: a practitioner extension of the J-Curve framework specifically addressing this assumption. The author brings to this analysis more than 25 years of experience delivering large-scale enterprise transformation programmes using agile methods. The Wiggly Curve does not contest the genuine advantage of agile delivery in reducing the magnitude of any individual change event. It contests the inference that smaller per-sprint disruption eliminates the need for change management — arguing instead that the cumulative effect of repeated small disruptions produces its own, less visible, performance gap.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the Kaizen/Kaikaku distinction and its relevance to the J-Curve. Section 3 presents the Wiggly Curve framework. Section 4 develops the cognitive load argument, drawing on Kahneman (2011) and the Zeigarnik effect. Section 5 situates the framework in the literature. Section 6 considers the implications for change management practice in an agile context. Section 7 looks forward to empirical research, and Section 8 concludes.

2. Background: The J-Curve, Kaizen, and Kaikaku

2.1 The J-Curve of Change

The J-Curve of Change (Viney, 2005) describes the trajectory of organisational performance during a period of planned technology-driven transformation. The framework identifies a characteristic pattern in which performance deteriorates following the introduction of change — the *performance dip* — before recovering and ultimately surpassing the prior baseline. The associated three management imperatives — managing stakeholder expectations, minimising the depth of the dip, and ensuring recovery — provide a practical framework for change leaders navigating this period.

The J-Curve was developed from the author's direct observation of post-go-live performance trajectories across multiple large-scale enterprise portal implementations in the early 2000s. Its central insight — that disruption is structural, not accidental, and that effective change management operates by shaping the dip rather than eliminating it — has proven durable across a wide range of technology implementation contexts.

2.2 Kaizen and Kaikaku

Two concepts from Japanese lean practice are essential to the argument of this paper. **Kaizen** (改善) denotes continuous incremental improvement: small, persistent gains that accumulate over time without fundamentally disrupting the system. **Kaikaku** (改革) denotes radical step-change: a deliberate disruption of the status quo in exchange for a leap to a significantly higher performance plateau.

The J-Curve is fundamentally a Kaikaku phenomenon. The organisation accepts a deep, temporary performance dip in exchange for a qualitatively better destination. The change is revolutionary rather than evolutionary. The job of the change manager in Kaikaku is to mitigate the impact of the disruption through awareness-building, training, interventions, and reward mechanisms — compressing the dip and accelerating recovery.

Agile practitioners are right to observe that their methodology is more Kaizen in character. Each sprint is small. Each increment is modest. Nobody is asked to absorb a large organisational disruption at once. It is from this observation that the inference of 'no change management required' is typically drawn. The Wiggly Curve challenges the validity of that inference.

3. The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change

3.1 Core Proposition

The central proposition of the Wiggly Curve is this: agile sprint cadence does not eliminate the J-Curve. It distributes it.

Instead of a single large performance dip associated with a big-bang go-live, the organisation undergoing agile transformation experiences a series of smaller oscillations, repeated at sprint cadence across the life of the programme. Each individual dip is modest. Each individual recovery is quick. But the cumulative effect on the people absorbing those changes is still significant — and substantially harder to observe, because no one is looking at the aggregate.

3.2 The Three-Curve Model

The Wiggly Curve model presents three trajectories for comparison:

- The Kaikaku J-Curve (grey): the baseline case of a single large transformation with no change management. Deep disruption, slow recovery, high human cost — but at least honest about what it demands of people.
- The Kaizen Wiggly Curve (purple): what agile practitioners typically assume will happen. Shallow oscillations at sprint cadence, gradual climb, arrival at the desired state with minimal disruption and no requirement for structured change management. An appealing picture.
- The Unmanaged Agile Outcome (dashed green): what actually happens when agile thinking ignores change management. Temporary adverse impact per sprint is indeed much smaller than in the Kaikaku case — but the cumulative trajectory plateaus short of the desired state. The gap between where the green line ends and where the purple line promised to arrive is the dead loss of poor adoption

Figure 1: The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change. Source: Viney (2026). Licensed under CC BY 4.0 (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

3.3 The Dead Loss of Poor Adoption

The gap labelled *dead loss of poor adoption* is the defining concept of the Wiggly Curve framework. It represents the performance benefit that was theoretically available from the agile transformation but was never realised — not because the technology failed, but because the cumulative human cost of repeated small disruptions was never managed. The organisation reaches a stable plateau, but below the desired state. The gap closes only with deliberate change management.

This framing is deliberately parallel to the J-Curve's 'valley of death' concept: both describe a failure mode arising from insufficient change management, but in different structural contexts. The valley of death is the risk that a Kaikaku dip becomes terminal. The dead loss of poor adoption is the risk that a Kaizen trajectory never reaches its destination.

3.4 The Duration Argument

A further contribution of the Wiggly Curve model is its challenge to the agile promise of speed. Every pitch for agile methodology includes an implicit claim of faster delivery: 'ship early', 'iterate often', 'faster to value'. Practitioners with experience of large-scale enterprise programmes delivered in agile will often acknowledge, quietly, that end-to-end, they typically take longer than their equivalent waterfall counterparts.

The reasons are structural: iterative delivery means some work is thrown away; some areas are reworked multiple times; scope evolves as understanding grows; and it can be genuinely difficult to agree when 'done' has been achieved. The Wiggly Curve model annotates this explicitly: the transition period under agile is typically longer than under a Kaikaku approach. Diagrams comparing agile and waterfall timelines that assume equivalent durations are, in the author's experience, optimistic.

4. The Cognitive Load Argument

4.1 Kahneman and Dual-Process Theory

The cognitive foundation of the Wiggly Curve argument draws on Kahneman's dual-process theory (Kahneman, 2011). System 1 thinking is fast, automatic, and effortless — the mode in which people operate under established habits and familiar routines. System 2 thinking is slow, deliberate, and effortful — the mode required when navigating unfamiliar territory, making conscious decisions, or adapting to change.

Each sprint release in an agile programme constitutes a fresh episode requiring System 2 engagement. Users must consciously adapt to new features, new workflows, new interfaces. This is not cognitively free. The cost is modest per sprint — but it is real, and it is repeated at two-week intervals for the life of the programme.

4.2 The Zeigarnik Effect and Change Intolerance

The **Zeigarnik effect** (Zeigarnik, 1927) describes the tendency of incomplete tasks to linger in working memory, creating a background cognitive load until they are resolved. In the context of agile delivery, each sprint release may introduce features or changes that users have not fully internalised before the next sprint arrives. The resulting accumulation of ‘not fully resolved items’ generates persistent cognitive load across the programme, even when each individual change is small.

Kahneman’s evidence points in the same direction: humans demonstrably prefer one large, finite change (even a painful one) to many small, repeated disruptions. Each small change is a fresh episode of System 2 engagement; the Zeigarnik effect means the previous episode may not yet be resolved when the next arrives; the cumulative result is **decision fatigue** and what the author terms **change intolerance**: a progressive reduction in users’ capacity and willingness to absorb further change.

By contrast, the Kaikaku change has a clear beginning, a defined end, and a recovery phase: once through the dip, the organisation can return to System 1 autopilot for an extended period. The agile programme, by design, offers no such closure.

The practical implication is that the aggregate cognitive cost of a series of small agile changes may substantially exceed the cost of a single large one — even where each individual increment appears trivially small. This is the cognitive mechanism underlying the dead loss of poor adoption.

5. Situating the Framework in the Literature

The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change extends and complements a body of literature on iterative change and technology adoption. Prosci’s ADKAR model (Hiatt, 2006) addresses adoption at an individual level, emphasising Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement — a sequence equally applicable to each sprint release as to a single large transformation. The agile change management literature, including Gover and Joiner (2017), has begun to address the specific challenge of embedding change management within iterative delivery frameworks, though much of this work focuses on the sprint-level rather than on programme-level cumulative effects.

The cognitive load literature provides a richer foundation. Sweller’s cognitive load theory (Sweller, 1988) identifies intrinsic, extraneous, and germane cognitive load as distinct sources of demand on working memory. In the agile context, each sprint release contributes extraneous cognitive load — the mental effort of adapting to new interfaces and workflows. The Zeigarnik effect compounds this by ensuring that unresolved prior changes remain as background load during subsequent sprints.

In the change management canon more broadly, the framework is related to Kotter’s observation that change fatigue is a primary cause of transformation failure (Kotter, 1996), and to the ‘implementation dip’ literature (Fullan, 2001). Where the Wiggly

Curve makes a distinctive contribution is in providing a visual and conceptual model for the specific dynamics of iterative change — a gap not adequately filled by either the J-Curve or the existing agile literature.

6. Implications for Change Management Practice

The Wiggly Curve does not argue against agile delivery. The reduction in per-sprint disruption is genuine and valuable, particularly where individual changes are modest in scope and clearly communicated. The argument is against the inference that smaller per-sprint disruption eliminates the need for change management. Agile does not make change management redundant. It makes it differently necessary.

Four principles for agile change management follow from the Wiggly Curve model:

- The change management function in an agile programme is not a project phase with a defined beginning and end. It is a persistent background capability for the life of the programme. Think of it as infrastructure, not initiative.
- The communications vehicle that works in an agile context is not the town hall or the programme newsletter. It is closer to Release Notes written in a user tone of voice — delivered at sprint cadence, focused on what just changed, what it means for you, and what to do differently. Not vision. Not strategy. Just: here is what happened this fortnight.
- Traditional change management operates at a remove from delivery — interpreting the programme to the business. Agile change management needs to be embedded in the sprint, not sat alongside it. The people doing it need to understand what was actually built.
- The agile change champion is often described as a User Adoption Manager or (from a vendor or partner perspective) a Customer Success Manager. The function is the same: minimise the period during which System 2 thinking is required; address loose ends before the Zeigarnik effect compounds them; close the gap between the purple and the green.

7. Future Research

The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change is, at present, a practitioner framework grounded in direct observation rather than systematic empirical evidence. The author's experience of large-scale agile transformations provides a robust qualitative foundation, but the framework would benefit substantially from empirical validation and extension.

The author is currently undertaking structured empirical research ahead of a new book, designed to address a genuine gap in the change management canon: which change interventions, adoption strategies, and reward mechanisms actually work in

organisations, and can be demonstrated by objective evidence? This research involves structured interviews and the gathering of data points across a range of companies and industry sectors, with a specific focus on the effectiveness of change management investment in iterative and agile delivery contexts.

Among the specific questions this research aims to address:

- Does the depth of the per-sprint performance oscillation vary systematically with sprint cadence, team size, or the nature of the change delivered?
- Is the dead loss of poor adoption measurable, and does it vary with the presence or absence of structured agile change management?
- Do organisations that implement dedicated agile change management functions achieve meaningfully better adoption outcomes than those that rely on the development team to manage user impact?
- What is the relationship between change intolerance and employee tenure, change history, and organisational culture?

These questions represent a research programme of genuine practical relevance. The change management field has long suffered from an abundance of frameworks and a scarcity of rigorous empirical evidence about what actually works. The Wiggly Curve provides a specific, testable model that could anchor such research.

8. Conclusion

The Wiggly Curve of Agile Change proposes that agile delivery does not eliminate the performance disruption described by the J-Curve of Change. It distributes it. The result is a series of small oscillations — modest per sprint, significant in aggregate — that, without deliberate change management, produce a measurable gap between the desired state and the end state actually achieved. This dead loss of poor adoption is the cost of assuming that the humans will sort themselves out.

The cognitive mechanism underlying this dynamic is well-established: Kahneman's dual-process theory explains why each sprint release demands System 2 engagement; the Zeigarnik effect explains why unresolved changes accumulate as background cognitive load; and the resulting change intolerance explains why adoption plateaus short of the desired state in unmanaged agile programmes.

Agile does not render change management redundant. It requires change management of a different kind: persistent rather than episodic, embedded rather than separate, written in user voice and honest about trade-offs. Slower than advertised. Occasionally retreading ground. But capable — done properly — of arriving at a destination that neither pure Kaikaku nor unmanaged Kaizen can reliably reach.

The dogmatic assertion that change management is someone else's problem in an agile programme will eventually find it becomes everyone's problem. Usually in the post-go-live period. Usually expensively.

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